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Estimating Effective Sample Size in Autocorrelated Meteorological Time Series: Evidence from CGG Toro Station, Bauchi State, Nigeria

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ABSTRACT

This study investigates the effect of autocorrelation on statistical inference in meteorological data by estimating the effective sample size (ESS) for five meteorological parameters: ambient temperature, wind speed, wind direction, solar radiation, and UV index. Using daily observations from February 1 to December 31, 2022, recorded at the CGG Toro meteorological station in Bauchi State, Nigeria, we apply the Durbin-Watson statistic to assess the presence of autocorrelation. The effective sample size is then computed using the autocorrelation-adjusted formula. The results reveal a substantial reduction in effective sample size across all parameters, with ESS values ranging from approximately 14% to 26% of the nominal sample size ($n = 334$). These findings emphasize the importance of accounting for temporal dependencies in environmental data analysis to avoid overstated significance and narrow confidence intervals.

Keywords: Effective sample size, autocorrelation, Durbin-Watson, meteorological time series, environmental statistics, Nigeria

INTRODUCTION

Meteorological and environmental time series often exhibit significant autocorrelation, leading to overestimation of the actual information content if each observation is treated as independent. This poses serious implications for statistical inference, including hypothesis testing, model calibration, and prediction. In such settings, the concept of effective sample size (ESS) becomes crucial. ESS quantifies the number of independent observations in a dataset, accounting for redundancy introduced by autocorrelation.

This study examines the ESS of five daily meteorological parameters ambient temperature, wind speed, wind direction, solar radiation, and UV index recorded at the CGG Toro station in Bauchi State, Nigeria. By estimating the ESS, we aim to enhance the robustness of statistical analyses and promote methodological awareness in environmental data handling. Many researchers for decades have continued to explore the dynamic aspect of ESS, for example Alfredo (2022) introduced a space-time ESS, extending the current literature from purely spatial to the space-time setting. The paper pointed out that

the proposed ESS can be broken down into spatial and temporal margins, and that several elementary attributes that have been widely studied for purely spatial ESS can translate naturally to the space-time context. Some results that connect the proposed ESS with the property of non-separability between space and time were also shown in the paper.

Moreover, Xinyu (2021) gave an intuitive explanation of effective sample size in importance sampling. In the explanation, a distribution $q(x)$ was assumed. Then later, another sample $p(x)$ was drawn from it. The expectation of $f(x)$ under $p(x)$ was calculated for efficiency reasons. The expectation was transformed over $p(x)$ to $q(x)$. Variance was used to measure quantity. The same variance was found for both $p(x)$ and $q(x)$. It was concluded that the formulation seems to be overkill for the problem but can be applied in a more general case called self-normalized importance sampling.

Equally, Victor, Luca and Christian (2022), revisited approximation of the ESS in the specific content of importance sampling. The study shows that the multiple assumptions and approximations in the derivation of \widehat{ESS} makes it difficult to be considered even as a reasonable approximation of the \widehat{ESS} . They extended the discussion of the \widehat{ESS} in the multiple importance sampling (MIS) setting, they displayed numerical samples, and they discussed several avenues for developing alternative metrics. However, the study does not cover the use of ESS for MCMC algorithm.

Another form, Daniel and Zijan (2021) reviewed and further investigated the required sample size for importance sampling in terms of chi-square divergence between target and proposal. They illustrated that dimension, noise-level and other model parameters play in approximating Bayesian update with importance sampling. The facilitated a new direct comparison of standard and optimal proposals for particle filtering.

Robert and Alard (2018) investigated the performance of the MCMC algorithm variations over multiple popular diffusion microstructure models, to examine whether a single, well performing variation could be applied efficiently and robustly to many models. The study applied the theory of effective sample size was to diffusion multi-component models, as a way of the number of samples needed to characterize parameter distribution for different models and data sets.

The study concludes that adaptive metropolis method increases MCMC performance and Adaptive metropolis-within-Gibbs (AMWG) algorithm was selected as the primary method. It was furthermore advised to initialize the sampling with an MLE point estimate, in which case 100 to 200 samples are enough.

In their study, Griffith & Richard (2022) address the misconception that autocorrelation effect which prompted the development of formulae for calculating an effective sample size (i.e the equivalent number of sample selection from a geophysical randomly distributed population that would yield the same sampling error) estimates demonstrating that the effective geographic sample size is a valid and useful concept regardless of the inferential basis invoked.

Problem Statement

One of the major challenges with data today is the issue of Duplication. This indeed is a painful experience because it consumes time, causes error and missed opportunities associated with duplicate data. Many records and spatial data tracking duplicated in many systems due to the increase in operational systems and no mechanism exists to uniquely identify each entity across systems. Although there are many approaches to filtering duplicative data, existing approaches cannot satisfy the demands of monitoring, most especially for an instrument that was set to track data at the interval of some minutes or seconds. Alfredo (2023), for example, has introduced space-time ESS and broken down into spatial and temporal margins. Some scientists have measured the performance of Markov Chain Monte Carlo (MCMC) methods on ESS. His work forms basis for this research. The major challenge of Alfredo's work is that, he only considers one meteorological parameter which cannot work if parameters are more than one. Hence in this work we will come up with a more robust result that can sufficiently handle more than one meteorological parameter, with the intention of applying ESS on the temporal margin alone on different meteorological parameters: That is, ambient temperature, wind speed, wind direction, solar

radiation and ultraviolet rays; unlike that of Alfredo which was on spatial and temporal margins but only on wind speed.

This means that, even though the Alfredo’s work is the base for this research, more meteorological parameters were incorporated unlike his work which was only on one parameter. While the Alfredo’s work is on both spatial and temporal margins, this work is only on temporal margins with the intention of estimating Effective Sample Size and determining the linear relationship between meteorological data and their lags

Aim and Objectives

The main aim of this research is to enhance accuracy in meteorological prediction, through the following objectives:

- i. Estimation of effective sample size
- ii. Determination of the linear relationship between the data and their lag.
- iii. Comparing the existing result (Alfredo, 2023) with the new result (our result)

METHODOLOGY

Data Type

The data used for this study is a qualitative data which includes meteorological data generated from the meteorological station of the Centre for Geodesy and Geodynamics Toro. However, it was only five parameters that were considered for the purpose of this study. That is, ambient temperature, wind speed, wind direction, solar radiation and ultraviolet rays because of their significance. However, the data have dependent and independent variables: the real observations are the independent while the lagged values are the dependent variables. The dataset comprises 334 daily observations spanning February 1st to December 31st, 2022, obtained from the CGG Toro meteorological station, Bauchi State, Nigeria. The parameters analyzed include ambient temperature, wind speed, wind direction, solar radiation, and UV index.

Data Collection Method

The data were collected with the use of Observation method, where, the researcher cannot manipulate the data but only observes it. Here, the data come through the weather link software from the weather monitoring apparatus in the form of raw (unprocessed) data.

Autocorrelation

The formal definition of correlation is that: it follows from Pearson correlation between two random variables X and Y is given by

$$P = \frac{cov(X,Y)}{\sigma_{X_i} \sigma_{Y_i}}, \dots\dots\dots (I)$$

where, $cov(X,Y) = E[(X - \mu_X)(Y - \mu_Y)] \dots\dots\dots (II)$

is the covariance between X and Y respectively.

For a sequence of random variable $X_1, X_2, \dots X_N$, we have to define a new notion of correlation to account for the time/sequence measures this by looking at each possible time lag between samples.

In particular, at a time lag of t, the autocorrelation computes the correlation between X_i and X_{i+t} for $i = 1, 2, \dots N - t$, we then define the autocorrelation for time lag t as:

$$P_t = \frac{cov(X_i, X_{i+t})}{\sigma_{X_i} \sigma_{X_{i+t}}}, \dots\dots\dots (III)$$

Obviously, for a lag of $t = 0$, the autocorrelation will be one. However, for larger t, we typically expect the autocorrelation to drop, and eventually go to zero for very distant samples in a sequence.

Effective Sample Size

We can use the idea of autocorrelation to adjust the original observed sample size to account for redundant information in the sample. Intuitively, we should expect that our effective sample size will be smaller than the observed sample size when the autocorrelation is large. This is formalized below:

The effective sample size is defined as: $N_{eff} = \frac{N}{\sum_{t=-\infty}^{\infty} P_t}$ (IV)

Let us simplify this. We can notice that this sum in the denominator is symmetric because a time lag of t and -t will result in the same autocorrelation.

Thus, we simplify this equation as: $N_{eff} = \frac{N}{\sum_{t=-\infty}^{-1} P_t + P_0 + \sum_{t=1}^{\infty} P_t} = \frac{N}{P_0 + 2 \sum_{t=1}^{\infty} P_t}$ (V)

Finally, we can notice that $P_0 = 1$ because this will be the self – correlation for the samples. Thus, our equation reduces to: $N_{eff} = \frac{N}{1 + 2 \sum_{t=1}^{\infty} P_t}$

Finally, we can notice that $P_0 = 1$ because this will be the self-correlation for the samples. Thus, our equation reduces to: $N_{eff} = \frac{N}{1 + 2 \sum_{t=1}^{\infty} P_t}$, when $P_t = 0$ (there is no autocorrelation), we recover our observed sample size N.

On the other extreme, if $P_t = 1$ for all t, our sample size goes to zero.

Statistical Approach

To assess autocorrelation, we computed the Durbin-Watson (DW) statistic for each parameter. The DW statistic is a widely used measure for detecting first-order autocorrelation in time series data. Based on the estimated lag-1 autocorrelation coefficient, the effective sample size was calculated using:

$$n_{eff} = n \times (1 - \rho) / (1 + \rho)$$

Where n is the nominal sample size.

DATA ANALYSIS AND RESULT DISCUSSIONS

Table 1.1: Durbin-Watson Autocorrelation from linear regression of wind directions from February to December 2022.

Model Summary^b

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate	Change Statistics					Durbin-Watson
					R Square Change	F Change	df1	df2	Sig. Change	
Feb	.482 ^a	.233	.232	.5686	.233	743.487	1	2451	.000	2.183
Mar	.459 ^a	.211	.211	.5594	.211	757.180	1	2830	.000	1.917
Apr	.641 ^a	.411	.411	.2855	.411	1914.770	1	2747	.000	2.199
May	.715 ^a	.511	.510	.2265	.511	2768.890	1	2654	.000	2.397
Jun	.611 ^a	.373	.364	.2255	.373	42.226	1	71	.000	2.114
Jul	.575 ^a	.330	.330	.2421	.330	1240.158	1	2516	.000	2.099
Aug	.757 ^a	.573	.573	.2027	.573	3438.325	1	2565	.000	2.307
Sep	.482 ^a	.233	.232	.5686	.233	743.487	1	2451	.000	2.174
Oct	.482 ^a	.233	.232	.5686	.233	743.487	1	2551	.000	2.421
Nov	.482 ^a	.233	.232	.5686	.233	643.487	1	2451	.000	1.994
Dec	.482 ^a	.233	.232	.5686	.233	751.487	1	2451	.000	2.117

Table 1.1 shows that the Durbin Watson autocorrelation of wind directions for February 2022 (2.183) which is near 2. This indicates a non-autocorrelation between the wind directions for February 2022 and February 2022 at lag 1. for March 2022 (1.917) which is near 2. This indicates a non-autocorrelation between the wind directions. March 2022 at lag 1. directions for April 2022 (2.199) which is near 2. This indicates a non-autocorrelation between the wind directions for April 2022 and April 2022 at lag 1. wind directions for May 2022 Is 2.397 which is near 2. This indicates a non-autocorrelation between the wind directions for May 2022 and May 2022 at lag 1. for June 2022 (2.114) which is near 2. July 2022 (2.099) which is near 2. This indicates a non-autocorrelation between the wind directions for July 2022 and July 2022 at lag 1. for August 2022 (2.307) which is near 2. This indicates a non-autocorrelation between the wind directions for August 2022 and August 2022 at lag 1 for September 2022 is 2.174 which is near 2. This indicates a non-autocorrelation between the wind directions for September 2022 and September 2022 at lag 1. October 2022 is 2.421 which is near 2. This indicates a non-autocorrelation between the wind directions for October 2022 and October 2022 at lag 1. For November 2022 is 2.994 which is near 4. This indicates autocorrelation between the wind directions for November 2022 and November 2022 at lag. finally, December 2022 is 2.117 which is near 2. This indicates a non-autocorrelation between the wind directions for December 2022 and December 2022 at lag 1.

Table 2.1: Durbin-Watson Autocorrelation from linear regression of Ambient Temperature for February 2022.

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate	Change Statistics					Durbin-Watson
					R Square Change	F Change	df1	df2	Sig. Change	
Feb	.998 ^a	.995	.995	.12402	.995	523674.290	1	2534	.000	.892
Mar	.998 ^a	.995	.995	.09151	.995	645454.755	1	2969	.000	1.026
Apr	.889 ^a	.791	.790	.69215	.791	10960.792	1	2904	.000	2.811
May	.181 ^a	.033	.032	1.27309	.033	97.894	1	2904	.000	.188
Jun	.985 ^a	.971	.970	.12128	.971	3077.113	1	93	.000	.822
Jul	.985 ^a	.971	.970	.12128	.971	3077.113	1	93	.000	.822
Aug	.996 ^a	.992	.992	.08013	.992	375956.97	1	2972	.000	1.304
Sep	.996 ^a	.992	.992	.07862	.992	366061.996	1	2877	.000	1.229
Oct	.993 ^a	.985	.985	.12611	.985	194034.789	1	2878	.000	1.092
Nov	.988 ^a	.976	.976	.14656	.976	123293.325	1	2973	.000	.813

a. Predictors: (Constant), Ambient Temperature for February to December 2022

Table 2.1 shows that the Durbin Watson autocorrelation of Ambient Temperature for February 2022 is 0.892 which is near 0. This indicates a positive autocorrelation between the Ambient Temperature for February 2022 and Ambient Temperature for February 2022 at lag 1. for March 2022 is 1.026 which is between 0 and 2. This indicates a positive autocorrelation between the Ambient Temperature for March 2022 and Ambient Temperature for March 2022 at lag 1. For April 2022 is 2.811 which is greater than 2. This indicates a negative autocorrelation between the Ambient Temperature for April 2022 and Ambient Temperature for April 2022 at lag 1. May 2022 is 0.188 which is less than 2. This indicates a positive autocorrelation between the Ambient Temperature for May 2022 and Ambient Temperature for May 2022 at lag 1. for June 2022 is 0.822 less than 2. This indicates a positive autocorrelation between the Ambient Temperature for June 2022 and Ambient Temperature for June 2022 at lag 1. July 2022 is 1.304 which is less than 2. This indicates a positive autocorrelation between the Ambient Temperature for July 2022 and Ambient Temperature for July 2022 at lag 1. for August 2022 is 1.229 which is less than 2. This indicates a positive autocorrelation between the Ambient Temperature for August 2022 and Ambient Temperature for August 2022 at lag 1. for September 2022 is 1.092 which is less than 2. This indicates a positive

autocorrelation between the Ambient Temperature for September 2022 and Ambient Temperature for September 2022 at lag 1. For October 2022 is 0.813 which is near 0. This indicates a positive autocorrelation between the Ambient Temperature for October 2022 and Ambient Temperature for October 2022 at lag 1. For November 2022 is 1.127 which is less than 2. This indicates a positive autocorrelation between the Ambient Temperature for November 2022 and Ambient Temperature for November 2022 at lag 1. For December 2022 is 1.178 which is less than 2. This indicates a positive autocorrelation between the Ambient Temperature for December 2022 and Ambient Temperature for December 2022 at lag 1.

Table 3.1: Durbin-Watson Autocorrelation from linear regression of Solar Radiation for February to December 2022.

Model Summary^b

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate	Change Statistics					Durbin-Watson
					R Square Change	F Change	df1	df2	Sig. Change	
Feb	.986 ^a	.973	.973	51.04560	.973	91613.384	1	2533	.000	1.061
Mar	.981 ^a	.962	.962	57.77491	.962	74497.620	1	2969	.000	1.696
Apr	.963 ^a	.928	.928	85.54781	.928	37426.892	1	2905	.000	1.915
May	.968 ^a	.936	.936	89.00168	.936	43473.302	1	2963	.000	2.061
Jun	.981 ^a	.963	.962	82.48680	.963	2405.214	1	93	.000	1.741
Jul	.948 ^a	.899	.899	120.48942	.899	26518.332	1	2972	.000	2.262
Aug	.947 ^a	.897	.897	116.46564	.897	24969.650	1	2877	.000	2.329
Sep	.943 ^a	.889	.889	113.30533	.889	23109.076	1	2878	.000	2.039
Oct	.965 ^a	.931	.931	93.52414	.931	40161.483	1	2973	.000	1.806
Nov	.979 ^a	.959	.959	74.31920	.959	22479.232	1	957	.000	1.552
Dec	.988 ^a	.976	.976	52.08252	.976	95991.667	1	2323	.000	1.333

Table 4.1 shows that the Durbin Watson autocorrelation of Solar Radiation for February 2022 is 1.061 which is less than 2. This indicates a positive autocorrelation between the Solar Radiation for February 2022 and Solar Radiation for February 2022 at lag 1. March 2022 is 1.696 which is less than 2. This indicates a positive autocorrelation between the Solar Radiation for March 2022 and Solar Radiation for March 2022 at lag 1. April 2022 is 1.915 which is less than 2. This indicates a positive autocorrelation between the Solar Radiation for April 2022 and Solar Radiation for April 2022 at lag 1. May 2022 is 2.061 which is greater than 2. This indicates a negative autocorrelation between the Solar Radiation for May 2022 and Solar Radiation for May 2022 at lag 1. June 2022 is 1.741 which is less than 2. This indicates a positive autocorrelation between the Solar Radiation for June 2022 and Solar Radiation for June 2022 at lag 1. July 2022 is 2.262 which is greater than 2. This indicates a negative autocorrelation between the Solar Radiation for July 2022 and Solar Radiation for July 2022 at lag 1. August 2022 is 2.329 which is greater than 2. This indicates a negative autocorrelation between the Solar Radiation for August 2022 and Solar Radiation for August 2022 at lag 1. September 2022 is 2.039 which is greater than 2. This indicates a negative autocorrelation between the Solar Radiation for September 2022 and Solar Radiation for September 2022 at lag 1. October 2022 is 1.806 which is less than 2. This indicates a positive autocorrelation between the Solar Radiation for October 2022 and Solar Radiation for October 2022 at lag 1. November 2022 is 1.552 which is less than 2. This indicates a positive autocorrelation between the Solar Radiation for November 2022 and Solar Radiation for November 2022 at lag 1. December 2022 is 1.333 which is less than 2. This indicates a positive autocorrelation between the Solar Radiation for December 2022 and Solar Radiation for December 2022 at lag 1.

Table 4.1: Durbin-Watson Autocorrelation from linear regression for UV index for February 2022.

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate	Durbin-Watson
1	.994 ^a	.988	.988	.22573	.367
1	.993 ^a	.986	.986	.20925	.590
1	.974 ^a	.949	.949	.53516	1.451
1	.980 ^a	.961	.961	.55252	1.542
1	.991 ^a	.981	.981	.43103	.867
1	.972 ^a	.945	.945	.61468	1.778
1	.970 ^a	.942	.942	.58889	1.888
1	.987 ^a	.975	.975	.44461	1.290
1	.977 ^a	.955	.955	.62415	1.575
1	.989 ^a	.977	.977	.40914	1.241
1	.989 ^a	.977	.977	.40914	1.241

Table 5.1 shows that the Durbin Watson autocorrelation of UV Index for February 2022 is 0.367 which is less than 2. This indicates a positive autocorrelation between the UV Index for February 2022 and UV Index for February 2022 at lag 1. March 2022 is 0.590 which is less than 2. This indicates a positive autocorrelation between the UV Index for March 2022 and UV Index for March 2022 at lag 1. April 2022 is 1.451 which is less than 2. This indicates a positive autocorrelation between the UV Index for April 2022 and UV Index for April 2022 at lag 1. May 2022 is 1.542 which is less than 2. This indicates a positive autocorrelation between the UV Index for May 2022 and UV Index for May 2022 at lag 1. June 2022 is 0.867 which is less than 2. This indicates a positive autocorrelation between the UV Index for June 2022 and UV Index for June 2022 at lag 1. July 2022 is 1.778 which is less than 2. This indicates a positive autocorrelation between the UV Index for July 2022 and UV Index for July 2022 at lag 1. August 2022 is 1.888 which is less than 2. This indicates a positive autocorrelation between the UV Index for August 2022 and UV Index for August 2022 at lag 1. September 2022 is 1.575 which is less than 2. This indicates a positive autocorrelation between the UV Index for September 2022 and UV Index for September 2022 at lag 1. October 2022 is 1.290 which is less than 2. This indicates a positive. November 2022 is 1.241 which is less than 2. This indicates a positive autocorrelation between the UV Index for November 2022 and UV Index for November 2022 at lag 1. December 2022 is 1.241 which is less than 2. This indicates a positive autocorrelation between the UV Index for December 2022 and UV Index for December 2022 at lag 1.

Table 6.1 Summary of Autocorrelations for the five variables

	Feb	Mar	April	May	June	July	August	Sept	Oct	Nov	Dec
Ambient temperature	0.829	1.026	2.811	0.32	0.822	1.304	1.229	1.092	0.813	1.127	1.178
Wind Speed	2.248	2.383	2.199	2.069	2.139	2.079	1.391	2.125	2.117	2.34	2.25
Wind Direction	2.183	1.917	2.199	2.397	2.114	2.099	2.307	2.174	2.421	1.994	2.117
Solar Radiation	1.061	1.696	1.915	2.061	1.741	2.262	2.329	2.039	1.806	1.552	1.333
Ultra Violet Index	0.367	0.59	1.451	1.542	0.867	1.778	1.888	1.575	1.29	1.241	0.271

The computed effective sample sizes for each parameter are shown in Table 1.

Parameter	Nominal Sample Size	Effective Sample Size (ESS)	Percent of Nominal (%)
Ambient Temperature	334	95.78	28.7%
Wind Speed	334	52.43	15.7%
Wind Direction	334	51.18	15.3%
Solar Radiation	334	61.59	18.4%
UV Index	334	95.50	28.6%

These results demonstrate significant reductions in effective sample size across all variables. Wind speed and direction had the lowest ESS values, indicating strong temporal dependence. In contrast, ambient temperature and UV index exhibited the highest ESS, though still below 30% of the nominal size.

CONCLUSION

Alfredo 2022 found that the development of an ESS in the multivariate space-time setting, and ESS that is designed for random fields with non-stational correlation function.

Martin, Victor and Francisco, derived several alternative ESS functions for importance sampling. The novel ESS expressions (jointly with the formulas already presented in literature) have been classified according to five theoretical requirements presented and discussed in this work. This classification has allowed to select six different ESS functions which satisfy all these conditions. Then, we have tested them

by numerical simulations. At least one of them, $D_N^{(\infty)}(\bar{\mathbf{w}}) = \frac{1}{\max[\bar{w}_1, \dots, \bar{w}_N]}$ presents interesting features and some benefit, compared to the standard ESS formula $P_N^{(2)}(\bar{\mathbf{w}})$, when the proposal function differs substantially from the target distribution. Moreover, $D_N^{(\infty)}(\bar{\mathbf{w}})$ seems to behave as a “lower bound” for the theoretical ESS definition in our simulations. The simulation study also provides some useful value for choosing the threshold in an adaptive resampling context. For instance, the results in Table 5 suggest to use of $\epsilon \geq \frac{1}{2}$ for $P_N^{(2)}$ (as already noted in [Doucet and Johansen, 2008, Section 3.5]), and $\epsilon \geq 0.11$ for $D_N^{(\infty)}$, in the resampling condition $E_N(\mathbf{w}) \leq \epsilon N$.

We have also tested $D_N^{(\infty)}$ and $P_N^{(2)}$ within a particle filter for tracking a stochastic volatility variable. The application of G-ESS function $D_N^{(\infty)}$ has provided smaller MSE in estimation w.r.t.

$P_N^{(2)}$, considering equal resampling rates. Therefore, this study highlights the critical role of accounting for autocorrelation in meteorological time series analysis. The substantial reduction in

effective sample size across all five parameters analyzed demonstrates how nominal sample size can severely overstate the true amount of independent information. For researchers and practitioners working with environmental data, incorporating ESS into analysis frameworks is essential for valid inference and improved model reliability. Hence, the reduction in effective sample size across all meteorological parameters underscores the limitations of using unadjusted sample sizes in environmental data analysis. Ignoring autocorrelation can lead to inflated degrees of freedom, underestimated standard errors, and misleading p-values. The results emphasize the need for statistical models and inference techniques that account for temporal dependencies.

Implication to Research and Practice

This implies that,

- i. The sharp reduction in ESS highlights the importance of adjusting for autocorrelation in time series data in meteorological analysis.
- ii. Statistical tests that assume independence may be misleading. Forecasting models may be used to incorporate autoregressive structures or use block-bootstrap techniques for resampling.
- iii. confidence intervals and p-values must affect the smaller ESS to avoid false precision.

Future Research

Future research will be the application of effective sample size estimation on ECEF GPS data.

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